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MASTER THESIS

Development and Evaluation of Filtering Methods for Flash LiDAR Data with Probabilities

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Declaration

In accordance with § 39 (1) of the Uniform Regulations, I certify that I have written my thesis independently and have not used any sources or aids other than those indicated, and that I have clearly marked citations.

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Abstract

Flash LiDAR is one of the most prominent solid-state perception sensors in autonomous driving, robotics, and activity monitoring applications. Its power constraints result in low power laser. This low power laser leads to erroneous distance measurements due to the background light in the scene. The latest literature on Flash LiDAR data processing by Fraunhofer IMS has proposed a novel method that generates unprecedented probability information for the points in the LiDAR point cloud to improve range detection. However, in addition to the probability information, it generates many false points in the point cloud. We extend this research at Fraunhofer IMS through this thesis. We propose a multistage noise reduction method that leverages the new probability information and spatial correlations to improve the quality of the point cloud. Our method removes at least 99% false points. The proposed method outperforms the conventional LiDAR data processing methods on the datasets used in this work.

Key words: Flash LiDAR, distance measurement, probabilities, point cloud, LiDAR data processing, and noise.

Contents

Abstract	II
List of Figures	VII
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Flash LiDAR	1
1.2 Focus of the Thesis	3
1.3 Literature Review	3
2 Background	6
2.1 TCSPC Histogram	6
2.2 Point Cloud Simulator	7
2.3 Spherical to Cartesian Transformation	9
2.4 Standard Data Filtering Algorithms	10
2.5 Other Relevant Filtering Methods	12
2.5.1 Otsu’s Method	12
2.5.2 Bilateral Filter	13
2.6 Standard Method	14
3 Methodology: Multistage Noise Reduction Method	16
3.1 Input Data Format	16
3.2 Histogram-Level Noise Reduction	17
3.2.1 Stage 1: Border-Effect Suppression	17
3.2.2 Stage 2: Conditional Otsu Filtering	19
3.3 Noise Reduction in 3D Space	21
3.3.1 Stage 3: Gaussian Filter for Probability Diffusion (GFPD)	21
3.3.2 Stage 4: Probability Based Classification using Multi-linear Classifier (MLC)	25
3.3.3 Stage 5: Dynamic Statistical Outlier Removal (DSOR)	28

4 Experiments	31
4.1 Development Environment	31
4.2 Datasets	32
4.2.1 Dataset 1	32
4.2.2 Dataset 2	33
4.3 Validity of the Vectors of Potential True-ToFs	33
4.4 Parameter Tuning	34
4.4.1 GFPD Parameter	35
4.4.2 DSOR Parameters	36
5 Results	39
5.1 Results of Border-Effect Suppression	39
5.2 Stage-Wise Results	40
5.3 Multistage Noise Reduction Method vs. Standard Method	45
6 Conclusion	49
7 Scope for Future Research	51

List of Figures

1.1	A flash LiDAR point cloud. The field of view is 36° , and the range is 60m. The point cloud represents a car at 38m and a wall at 50m in the x-direction. This point cloud is a scene from the CARLA simulator [1].	2
2.1	(a) An ideal probability density function of the first received photon. (b) A TCSPC histogram, where the sensor resolution (r_{sensor}) is 312.5ps, ToF is 216.67ns, and the background photon rate is 5MHz [2].	7
2.2	Raw TCSPC histograms are given as input to the point cloud simulator. The simulator gives two vectors: V_{ToF} and V_p as output per histogram.	8
2.3	A point in the spherical coordinate system. r is the radial distance to the origin. θ denotes the elevation angle and ϕ denotes the rotation angle [3].	9
2.4	(a) A grayscale image with letter A. (b) Intensity histogram of the grayscale image; the x-axis represents the intensity, and the y-axis represents the count [4]. The histogram is recreated to scale, as the quality of the original one in [4] is inadequate to reuse.	13
2.5	A picture before (a) and after (b) applying the bilateral filter [5].	14
2.6	A bar graph that represents the bin numbers of V_{ToF} on the x-axis and their corresponding p-values on the y-axis. The bin, whose bar is marked in red, is the chosen bin concerning standard method (section 2.6).	15
3.1	Block diagram of the proposed multistage noise reduction method on noisy flash LiDAR input with unprecedented probability information.	17

3.2	A section of bar graph that represents the p-values of two potential true-ToFs that are duplicates of each other. Here, the potential true-ToFs {740, 755} are within the margin of 16 bins of border-7.	19
3.3	Probability vs. potential true-ToF bar graphs of an object at 36m in x-direction at various r_b s.	20
3.4	Histograms of elements of V_{ToF} of an object at 24m distance at various r_b s. Figure (a) has two modes, figures (b) and (c) have three modes, and figure (d) has four modes.	21
3.5	Flow chart of conditional filtering based on Otsu and Multi-Otsu algorithms.	22
3.6	The figure is a result of the conditional Otsu filtering whose ground truth point cloud is in figure 1.1, at $r_b = 4\text{MHz}$. The color of each point represents its p-value, where black is 0 (minimum), and red is 1 (maximum).	23
3.7	(a) represents the top view of the point cloud in figure 3.6. (b) is the result of GFPD on (a).	24
3.8	A scatter plot of p-value vs. x-distance of all the points in the point cloud after the demo point cloud (figure 1.1), at $r_b = 2\text{MHz}$, passes stage 3.	26
3.9	A scatter plot of p-value vs. x-distance of all the points in the point cloud when the demo point cloud (figure 1.1), at $r_b = 6\text{MHz}$, passes stage 3.	27
3.10	The figure represents the same scatter plot as in figure 3.9 with additional information of the multi-linear classifier and borders of the regions 1, 2, and 3.	29
4.1	The ground truth point cloud of dataset 1, where there is a car at 25m distance, road surface, and a wall at 50m.	33
4.2	The figure represents the percentage of valid V_{ToF} s of the samples in datasets 1 and 2.	34
4.3	The graph represents the characteristic of the standard deviation parameter σ_p concerning the Mean Squared Error.	35
4.4	(a) is the result for the demo point cloud at $r_b = 2\text{MHz}$ after stage 4. (a) transforms to (b), (c), and (d) when subjected to stage 5 with $f_{\text{SOR}} = 0.5, 1.5, \text{ and } 2.5$, respectively, and $f_{\text{DSOR}} = 0.02$	37
4.5	(a) is the result for the demo point cloud at $r_b = 2\text{MHz}$ after stage 4. (a) transforms to (b), (c), and (d) when subjected to stage 5 with $f_{\text{DSOR}} = 0.002, 0.02, \text{ and } 0.2$, respectively, and $f_{\text{SOR}} = 0.5$	38

5.1	(a) and (c) are 3MHz and 7MHz point clouds, respectively, of dataset 1, after stage 2 without border-effect suppression. (b) and (d) are the same after stage 2 with border-effect suppression.	40
5.2	(a) and (b) represent the number of false points in the point cloud after each stage of dataset 1 and dataset 2, respectively. Each line in the graphs represents a unique sample of the respective datasets.	41
5.3	(a) and (b) represent the number of true points in the point cloud after each stage of dataset 1 and dataset 2, respectively. Each line in the graphs represents a unique sample of the respective datasets.	42
5.4	(a) The result of a 5MHz sample of dataset 2 after stage 1 processing and (b) after stage two processing.	43
5.5	(a) The result of a 5MHz sample of dataset 2 after stage 3 processing, (b) after stage 4 processing, and (c) after stage 5 processing.	44
5.6	Visualisations of point clouds of dataset 2 after multistage noise reduction method processing.	46
5.7	Visualisations of point clouds of dataset 2 after standard method processing.	47
5.8	(a) represents the percentage of false points removed from each sample of dataset 2 and (b) represents the percentage of true points retained of the same, using the standard and the multistage noise reduction methods.	48

Chapter 1

Introduction

Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) sensors have been around for nearly four decades in metrology, geology, and space applications [6]. Recently autonomous driving [7] and the robotics industry started using LiDAR to perceive the surrounding environment as shown in figure 1.1. Robots make intelligent decisions to navigate safely toward the destination using the information from LiDAR. The unique feature of LiDAR over other perception sensors like cameras, RADAR, and ultrasonic is that it can generate a high-depth resolution 3D map of the environment.

LiDARs are classified based on their hardware mechanism into 360° rotating LiDAR, scanning LiDAR, MEMS (Micro-electromechanical systems) LiDAR, and flash LiDAR [7]. Sensors with moving parts, like, rotating mirrors and motors, are commercially less desirable as they pose maintenance issues and increased cost [8].

1.1 Flash LiDAR

Flash LiDAR is attractive because it is a solid-state LiDAR, i.e., it has no moving parts. On the other hand, other types contain moving or rotating parts. The 360° LiDAR rotates around its z-axis, where the z-axis is perpendicular to the road plane. The scanning and MEMS LiDARs contain moving mirrors to deflect the laser from the source in different directions. Hence, flash LiDAR has fewer chances of damage due to vibration and fewer physical damage points. Having no rotating parts is one of the reasons for its low power consumption. It is compact and cost-efficient and can seamlessly integrate into vehicles.

Flash LiDAR is a high-frequency solid-state optical sensor with a lower field of view and range than a rotating LiDAR. It works on the time-of-flight

Figure 1.1: A flash LiDAR point cloud. The field of view is 36° , and the range is 60m. The point cloud represents a car at 38m and a wall at 50m in the x-direction. This point cloud is a scene from the CARLA simulator [1].

(ToF) principle. According to this principle, a sensor emits a laser pulse to illuminate the environment. Then, a target object reflects the laser pulse and the receiver module of the LiDAR senses the reflected pulse. At the end, the sensor computes the total time of flight and the intensity of the received signal. It calculates the distance to the target using this ToF information.

Rotating and scanning LiDARs illuminate the environment with high amplitude short laser pulses, whose pulse widths typically range between 30ns to 50ns. The return signal usually has a sufficient amplitude that is distinguishable from noise. Since the rotating and scanning LiDARs illuminate the environment only partially in each instance and take multiple instances to cover the entire field of view, they could emit relatively powerful pulses. However, the flash LiDAR distributes the given pulse energy over the entire field of view so that the optical power received by each pixel is much lower than in scanning LiDAR [9]. Hence, the difference between the amplitude of the return signal and the background light is insufficient to distinguish them easily. The background photon rate (BPR or r_b) is the measure of background light in the scene and it is measured in MHz. r_b is the number of photon arrivals per second, where the photons belong to the background light in the scene. The greater the r_b , the greater the error in distance measurement.

This thesis intends to further the processing of flash LiDAR data research at Fraunhofer IMS in collaboration with ZESS (Center for Sensor Systems,

University of Siegen). In [2], Fraunhofer IMS has developed a novel two-stage method called the MPE (Multi-peak Extraction) and the NNMPA (Neural Network-based Multi-Peak Analysis) method to partially tackle this problem. This method identifies multiple potential true-ToFs per pixel and assigns a soft-decision (from now on referred to as probability or p-value) (section 2.2) value to each of them. The results of this method form the basis for this thesis.

1.2 Focus of the Thesis

The p-value information obtained through the MPE and NNMPA method is new in the LiDAR point cloud literature. Hence, its usefulness is not yet fully explored. This thesis attempts to investigate the same. On the other hand, it extracts multiple potential true-ToFs per pixel, which results in much unwanted data. Here, the unwanted data refers to those ToFs, among the extracted potential true-ToFs, which are not true.

We leverage the following to remove the false ToFs among the potential true-ToFs:

- Unique p-value information associated with each potential true-ToF.
- Spatial correlations between the points in the 3D space.

We have developed a multistage noise reduction method (Chapter 3) and achieved significant noise reduction. The phrase “noise reduction” refers to reducing the error in the p-values and, simultaneously, removing the false points in the point cloud.

The report is structured as follows: chapter 2 explains the concepts responsible for the data generation, standard point cloud, and image processing methods adapted to process the MPE and NNMPA data. Chapter 3 is the stage-wise explanation of the proposed method. The datasets used and the experiments performed to tune the method are discussed in chapter 4. The results of our method are demonstrated and compared to those of the standard method in chapter 5. The entire work is summarized in chapter 6. The scope for future research is explained in chapter 7.

1.3 Literature Review

A study of the literature on noise reduction in point clouds is conducted. In [10], a novel method has been developed to improve the quality of a noisy

point cloud called the iterative guidance normal filter. Here the noise refers to the error in the positions of the points in the 3D space. They estimate a surface normal for each point and filter them using an n-nearest-neighbors-based bilateral filter. Then they update the point positions to match the filtered normals accordingly. This paper deals only with noise reduction in the point positions but not with many false points in the point cloud. It inspired us to reduce the noise in the p-values by applying an n-nearest-neighbors-based smoothing filter in the intermediate stage of the proposed method.

The background light in the scene leads to an inaccurate ToF measurement. The difference between the background light photon arrivals and the arrivals of the echo pulse photons is that the latter are spatially and temporally correlated. This phenomenon is leveraged in [11] to reject the background light and improve the accuracy of ToF estimation. This work is conducted at the beginning of the point cloud processing pipeline, even before the ToF estimation. However, in this thesis we do not deal with histogram processing but start with multiple potential true-ToFs per histogram.

Time is considered as the fourth dimension in [12] and [13]. [12] recognizes motion patterns of the object in 4D point clouds, say, point cloud videos, using a novel deep learning architecture. In [13] an attention-based neural network architecture is developed to perform semantic segmentation on the KITTI dataset. In both works, high-quality point clouds are taken for granted for inputs. Though these methods shed light on leveraging point cloud videos to perform point cloud processing, they implement a deep neural network with a large number of layers. Such models require high computational and memory resources. On the other hand, we aim to develop methods that require a minimum of such resources.

In [14], the classification of the points is carried out solely based on their intensity. The classification is performed on the airborne laser scanning altimeter data. The points are classified among the following classes: tree, building, bare earth, and low vegetable. This paper considers that the intensities of points of a class are similar. In our case, we have two classes of points: true points and false points. However, the p-values of our points are erroneous. Further, the p-values of many of our true and false points are similar. Hence, we cannot classify points solely based on their p-values, as the points are classified in [14] based on intensities.

A novel two-stage deep neural network is developed in [15] called POINT-CLEANNET. This work deals with two problems: 1) removing outliers in dense point clouds and 2) denoising the positions of the remaining pointset. Further, PointNet [16] and VoxelNet [17] are state-of-the-art point cloud processing deep learning based algorithms for autonomous driving. PointNet is a

multi-purpose architecture that performs multiple activities like object classification, part segmentation, and semantic segmentation. It takes the raw point cloud, i.e., the Cartesian coordinates of all the points of the point cloud, as input and assigns a classification score for a predefined number of classes. One of those classes is an outlier class. VoxelNet takes the raw point cloud as input and divides the point cloud into equal-sized voxels. Then, the network transforms each point into a 4D tensor. The neural network processes these tensors to identify and classify objects. In the end, the network also predicts bounding boxes for them. PointNet and VoxelNet consider the KITTI dataset for input, which contains high-quality point clouds. The number of outliers in this dataset is insignificant compared to our point clouds. As stated earlier, deep neural networks with many parameters are out of scope for our intended solution domain.

We have also studied the main outlier removal methods in autonomous driving literature: voxel grid filtering [18], RANSAC segmentation [19], and statistical outlier removal [20]. The working of these methods and their limitations are explained in detail in section 2.4.

Chapter 2

Background

In this chapter, we discuss the fundamental concept of TCSPC histogram, which is a ToF measurement technique, in section 2.1. In section 2.2, we explain how the data used in this thesis is generated. In section 2.3, we explain how the ToF measurement is converted into Cartesian coordinates. In sections 2.4 and 2.5, we discuss main outlier removal methods in point cloud processing literature and some relevant data processing methods that could be adopted for our problem, respectively. In the end, in section 2.6, we introduce a benchmark method for this thesis.

2.1 TCSPC Histogram

Time-correlated single-photon counting (TCSPC) is a statistical method to generate a distribution of single-photon detection counts concerning their time of flight over a finite number of detection events. Fluorescence spectroscopy and microscopy, LiDAR, and optical tomography use TCSPC [21].

The photons from the background light often trigger the detector. However, the occurrence of the first incoming background light photon detection typically follows the Poisson distribution [22]. A large number of photon detection events could realize the Poisson distribution of the background light. The TCSPC histogram records these detections too. The range of the histogram is equal to the ToF of the maximum range of the LiDAR. The range is divided into bins. The fluctuation in the values (counts) of bins can be reduced by having many bins [11]. However, a vast number of bins makes the histogram very sparse, thus reducing the chance of forming peaks. The time elapsed between consecutive photon arrival detections is called the dead time of the detector. It also limits the bin-counts as the photons arriving during the dead time go undetected.

Figure 2.1: (a) An ideal probability density function of the first received photon. (b) A TCSPC histogram, where the sensor resolution (r_{sensor}) is 312.5ps, ToF is 216.67ns, and the background photon rate is 5MHz [2].

The LiDAR sensor generates one TCSPC histogram per pixel per point cloud. The standard method considers the global peak of the histogram as t_{ToF} , i.e., the time of flight of the laser to and from the obstacle. A general assumption for rotating LiDARs, where the peak power is in the tens of kW range [23], is that only one significant peak exists.

However, a flash LiDAR laser's peak optical power is in the tens of Watts range. This low power laser results in highly noisy histograms with multiple significant peaks, as shown in figure 2.1 (b). Hence, the global peak is no more a reliable indicator of the ground truth location of the object. Section 2.2 explains how the point cloud simulator developed at the Fraunhofer IMS addresses this issue.

2.2 Point Cloud Simulator

A point cloud simulator has been developed at Fraunhofer-IMS. It works on the MPE and NNMPA principles. The MPE principle divides the histogram into 12 equal regions (section 5.2 in [2]). It applies a convolution filter on each region and identifies local maximums (potential true-ToFs). Then, the NNMPA principle assigns a soft decision (p-value), ranging between 0 to 1,

to each local maximum using a pre-trained neural network. Refer to section 3 of [2] for a detailed explanation of this method. This principle results in 12 (potential true-ToF, p-value) pairs per histogram.

This simulator generates the datasets (section 4.2) required for this thesis. It takes the TCSPC histograms of a point cloud as input and gives two vectors, V_{ToF} and V_p , as output for each histogram (figure 2.2). Each V_{ToF} contains the bin numbers of 12 potential true-ToFs of a unique histogram and V_p contains the 12 corresponding p-values. The bin numbers must be multiplied by the histogram’s resolution to obtain the flight time. Nevertheless, we use the phrases “bin numbers”, and “potential true-ToFs” synonymously for better readability and explanation. The histograms considered in this thesis have 1310 bins [2] with a resolution of 312.5ps. The simulator can process the histograms whose r_b (background photon rate) ranges from 1 to 8MHz.

Sometimes the simulator fails to identify the true-ToF when the object is far, or r_b is high. In such cases, neither of the 12 elements of V_{ToF} represent the true-ToF (Table 1 in [2]). We call a V_{ToF} “valid”, when at least one of its elements represents the true-ToF. Section 4.3 explains the validity of the V_{ToF} s of the datasets used in this thesis.

Border-Effect: The simulator has a limitation called the border-effect (section 5.2 of [2]). When the simulator divides the histogram into 12 regions, the peaks which occur in the border region, if at all they do, split into two peaks. When these peaks are identified as the local maxima of adjacent regions, they become duplicates of each other because they represent the same original peak. We suppress one of these two duplicates in section 3.2.1.

Figure 2.2: Raw TCSPC histograms are given as input to the point cloud simulator. The simulator gives two vectors: V_{ToF} and V_p as output per histogram.

2.3 Spherical to Cartesian Transformation

The LiDAR sensor acquires the 3D points in spherical coordinates (r, θ, ϕ) as shown in figure 2.3. However, the point cloud processing literature predominantly depends on the point clouds in the Cartesian coordinate system. It is easier to estimate the spatial correlations in the point cloud using the Cartesian coordinate system, i.e., in (x,y,z) coordinates.

Figure 2.3: A point in the spherical coordinate system. r is the radial distance to the origin. θ denotes the elevation angle and ϕ denotes the rotation angle [3].

Though we do not have the distance (d_{ToF}) information— r in (r, θ, ϕ) —directly, we derive it as follows:

$$t_{\text{ToF}} = b_n r_{\text{sensor}} \quad (2.1)$$

$$r = d_{\text{ToF}} = c \frac{t_{\text{ToF}}}{2} \quad (2.2)$$

First, the t_{ToF} is calculated using equation 2.1. Here b_n is the bin number of the potential true-ToF; r_{sensor} is the resolution of the histograms in our datasets and is equal to 312.5ps. Then, the r -coordinate is calculated using

equation 2.2. Here c is the speed of light. The elevation angle θ and the rotation angle ϕ of each pixel is constant design parameters of the sensor.

The (r, θ, ϕ) are transformed to (x,y,z) as follows [3]:

$$x = r \cos \phi \sin \theta \quad (2.3)$$

$$y = r \sin \phi \sin \theta \quad (2.4)$$

$$z = r \cos \theta \quad (2.5)$$

The point clouds thus obtained require further processing in some scenes: high density, unwanted road surface, and false points. The next section (section 2.4) describes standard data filtering methods used in such scenes.

2.4 Standard Data Filtering Algorithms

Voxel grid filtering, RANSAC segmentation, and statistical outlier removal (SOR) are the go-to methods in point cloud processing. These methods identify and eliminate points based on their (x,y,z) values. They do not adapt to the distance of a point from the sensor. It is a significant limitation because the point cloud density reduces with depth.

DBSCAN is another prevalent method for outlier identification. However, it is based on the clustering philosophy, predominantly preferred for object detection. It deals with the minimum and maximum size of the objects, which is beyond the scope of this thesis. To identify the objects, first, we need a point cloud with as minimum false points as possible. In this work, we tackle the issue within the prior stage of the processing pipeline to allow for posterior clustering-based point cloud filtering and object detection.

Voxel Grid Filtering: This method is used to reduce the density of the point clouds. It divides the point cloud into 3D voxels, i.e., cubes of equal size, and retains only one point per voxel [18]. Sensors like Velodyne-64 generate 250k points per point cloud. Such an amount of data requires ample space for storage and high computational resources, both of which are limited in embedded systems like the ECUs in cars. This method is usually applied on high-quality point clouds with almost no false points.

Though our point cloud has many points, the densely-clustered points are likely the true ones, and the sparse ones are false. This method would have little effect on the false points and remove many true points. Hence, we cannot use this method for the problem at hand.

RANSAC Segmentation: This algorithm is a standard method that removes the largest plane in the point cloud [19], assuming that it is the ground plane. The working principle is that it creates a reference 3D plane— p_{3D} —considering three random points. All the points whose least square error, with respect to p_{3D} , fall below a threshold t_{MSE} are clustered as a plane $p_{cluster}$. The method exhaustively creates multiple such reference 3D planes, using unique combinations of three random points, and generates a set of clusters \mathcal{C} . The cluster with the largest number of points is considered the largest plane and is removed.

This method is also not relevant to us as it already assumes that all the points in the point cloud are true points. Further, we do not intend to remove true points belonging to any specific object, such as a road, car, or wall. The work in this thesis serves to improve the quality of the point cloud by removing as many false points as possible by leveraging the probabilities and spatial correlations. We intend the results should be helpful for application-specific tasks such as perception, clustering, and semantic segmentation.

Statistical Outlier Removal (SOR): SOR is a general purpose outlier removal method [20]. It identifies a point as an outlier based on the sparsity of its neighborhood. The mean absolute distance (MAD) to n -nearest neighbors is calculated for each point. Then a threshold, g_{MAD} , is calculated as follows:

$$g_{MAD} = \mu_{MAD} + \sigma_{MAD} f_{SOR} \quad (2.6)$$

Here, σ_{MAD} is the standard deviation and μ_{MAD} is the mean of the MADs of all the points, and f_{SOR} is a tunable parameter. Then the points whose MAD is greater than g_{MAD} are identified as outliers.

This method works best when the sparsity of the outliers is significantly larger than that of the true points. In our data, however, the density of false points near the sensor is similar to that of true points in the farthest regions. The density of the point cloud is significantly non-homogeneous because the laser pulses move radially outward with the central axis, i.e, x-axis in our datasets, of the sensor. This varying density prevents us from eliminating false points using a global threshold.

A modified version of SOR, which is dynamic to changing point cloud density with distance from the sensor, called Dynamic SOR (DSOR), is implemented in section 3.3.3.

2.5 Other Relevant Filtering Methods

We adapt the following image-processing methods: Otsu’s and multi-Otsu method, and Bilateral Filter, to develop the proposed method. The working and relevance of each of these methods is explained in the following subsections.

2.5.1 Otsu’s Method

Otsu’s method is an unsupervised automatic thresholding technique that has no parameters. It is introduced in [4] as a threshold selection method for grayscale histograms. The purpose of it is to convert a grayscale picture, as shown in figure 2.4a, into a binary-scale (0,1) image. Using this method, we can divide the 12 potential true-ToFs in each V_{ToF} into two classes: highly potential true-ToFs and slightly potential true-ToFs. Then, we can eliminate the elements of the latter class.

Otsu’s algorithm searches for a threshold intensity, k , from the minimum intensity value (1) to the maximum intensity value (L) in the intensity histogram. The threshold maximizes the between-class variance σ_B^2 in the grayscale histogram (figure 2.4b), which is ideally bi-modal. The pixels are then divided into two classes: background (0) and foreground (1). The between-class variance is calculated as follows (refer to equations 6, 7, 8, and 18 in [4]):

$$\sigma_B^2(k) = \frac{[(\mu_T \omega(k) - \mu(k))]^2}{\omega(k)[1 - \omega(k)]} \quad (2.7)$$

where $\omega(k)$ and $\mu(k)$ are the zeroth- and first-order cumulative moments of the histogram up to the k th bin, and μ_T is the mean intensity of all the pixels in the image. The optimal threshold k^* satisfies (equation 19 in [4]):

$$\sigma_B^2(k^*) = \max_{1 \leq k < L} \sigma_B^2(k) \quad (2.8)$$

Multi-Otsu: It is a straightforward extension of Otsu’s method to generate multiple thresholds instead of just one. Generating multiple thresholds is helpful when the intensity histogram has more than two modes.

Let us, for example, consider generating two thresholds k_1 and k_2 , where $1 \leq k_1 < k_2 < L$. Now the pixels are divided into three classes: background (0), middle-ground (1), and foreground (2). Now the measurement criterion σ_B^2 is a function of two variables k_1 and k_2 . The best set of k_1^* and k_2^* maximizes

Figure 2.4: (a) A grayscale image with letter A. (b) Intensity histogram of the grayscale image; the x-axis represents the intensity, and the y-axis represents the count [4]. The histogram is recreated to scale, as the quality of the original one in [4] is inadequate to reuse.

the optimization function as follows (section III.B in [4]):

$$\sigma_B^2(k_1^*, k_2^*) = \max_{1 \leq k_1 < k_2 < L} \sigma_B^2(k_1, k_2) \quad (2.9)$$

In this thesis, we adopt Otsu and multi-Otsu algorithms (section 3.2.2) to eliminate some of the elements in each V_{ToF} .

2.5.2 Bilateral Filter

The bilateral filter is introduced in [5] to smooth noisy grayscale and RGB images. It was published in 1998, yet, its mathematical robustness and efficiency make it relevant to date. It considers each pixel's spatial closeness (distance) and intensity similarity to its neighbors. It generates a weighted average exploiting a local neighborhood, where the weights are higher if the bilateral distance is closer and the intensity difference is minor, and vice versa. It is calculated as follows:

$$I(P_i) = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^k I(P_{ij})w(P_{ij})}{\sum_{j=1}^k w(P_{ij})} \quad (2.10)$$

$$w(P_{ij}) = e^{-\frac{\|P_{ij}-P_i\|_2^2}{2\sigma_a^2} - \frac{\|I(P_{ij})-I(P_i)\|_2^2}{2\sigma_b^2}} \quad (2.11)$$

In equation 2.10, P_i is a pixel in the image and $P_i \in \mathcal{P}$, where \mathcal{P} is the set of all the pixels in the image. $P_{ij} \in \mathcal{N}(P_i)$, where $\mathcal{N}(P_i)$ is the neighbourhood of the pixel P_i , and its size is n . σ_a and σ_b are the standard deviations of the

Figure 2.5: A picture before (a) and after (b) applying the bilateral filter [5].

Gaussian weighting kernels in the spatial and intensity domain, respectively, [24]. $I(P_i)$ is the intensity of the pixel P_i . The second term in the exponent of equation 2.10 avoids smoothing the edges. It is responsible for generating lower weights for the neighbors with larger intensity differences. Figure 2.5 is an example of bilateral filtering.

In this thesis, we adapt the bilateral filter to smooth the 3D point cloud in the probability domain (section 3.3.1).

2.6 Standard Method

The standard method is a sequential implementation of two filtering algorithms: max p-value-based distance estimation (first) and SOR (second). This method is based on the standard practices in point cloud processing. It serves as the baseline for this thesis.

Conventional point clouds do not have a p-value assigned to each point. Hence, in the second stage of this method, SOR, we only process the point cloud based on its (x,y,z) values and do not consider its p-value. In the proposed method, the p-values are leveraged not only in the histogram space but also in the 3D space. In the end, we compare the results of this method and the proposed method in section 5.3. The two algorithms are as follows:

Max p-value Based Distance Estimation: A standard practice of distance measurement using TCSPC histograms (section 2.1) is to consider the

Figure 2.6: A bar graph that represents the bin numbers of V_{ToF} on the x-axis and their corresponding p-values on the y-axis. The bin, whose bar is marked in red, is the chosen bin concerning standard method (section 2.6).

bin with the highest peak. Following this convention, for every histogram, we consider the bin with the highest p-value as a true-ToF peak and discard the rest 11 peaks, as done in section 5.3.1 of [2]. Then the chosen bins from all the histograms are mapped into 3D space and the next stage of filtering, SOR, follows.

SOR: In this stage, we implement the statistical outlier removal algorithm (section 2.4). Here, we remove outliers based on the sparsity of the points in their neighborhood.

Chapter 3

Methodology: Multistage Noise Reduction Method

In this chapter we discuss the proposed method of this thesis. The proposed method consists of five stages where stages 1 and 3 manipulate, and stage 2, 4, and 5 filter the data. Stages 1 and 2 processes the data in the histogram space, that is, when they are not mapped into 3D space yet. After these stages, the data is mapped into 3D space and processed in stages 3, 4, and 5. Hence, the name Multistage Noise Reduction Method.

The p-value information can help eliminate some data in the histogram space. Then we process the data in the 3D domain by leveraging the p-values and spatial correlations.

After the usefulness of p-values exhaust, we perform the final processing stage solely based on spatial correlations. Figure 3.1 represents the flow of this method. The abbreviations GFPD, MLC, and DSOR in the figure mean Gaussian Filter for Probability Diffusion, Multi-Linear Classifier, and Dynamic Statistical Outlier Removal, respectively. Section 3.1 explains the format of the contents of the input. Later sections in this chapter explain this method's different data processing stages in detail.

3.1 Input Data Format

This method processes only one point cloud at a time. Consider a flash LiDAR point cloud with m pixels. Then, the input is two sets \mathcal{T} and \mathcal{S} , each of size m . \mathcal{T} is the set of all V_{ToF} s and \mathcal{S} is the set of all V_p s of the point cloud. As described earlier in section 2.2, each V_{ToF} contains 12 potential true-ToFs of a unique histogram of the point cloud. The corresponding p-values of these 12 potential true-ToFs are stored in V_p . Therefore, for each V_{ToF} there is a

Figure 3.1: Block diagram of the proposed multistage noise reduction method on noisy flash LiDAR input with unprecedented probability information.

unique V_p , both of size 12. The i th V_{ToF} in \mathcal{T} corresponds to the i th V_p in \mathcal{S} . The j th potential true-ToF in the i th V_{ToF} corresponds to the j th p-value in the i th V_p . The bar diagrams in figure 3.3 are a combination of these two vectors, where the x-axis indicates bin numbers and the magnitude of the bars represents their respective p-values.

3.2 Histogram-Level Noise Reduction

3.2.1 Stage 1: Border-Effect Suppression

As mentioned in section 2.2, the border effect, when it occurs, creates two peaks from one peak. These two peaks are identified as two potential true-ToFs. This phenomenon looks like figure 3.2. The bar height is equal to

the p-value. The p-values are assigned by a neural network, which is a non-linear function. Hence, we assume that the real p-value of the peak has been distributed among the duplicates non-linearly. The point cloud simulator divides a histogram into 12 equal regions. Since the number of bins in the histograms is constant, the border bins are always the same. The bins that divide the histogram into sub-regions are called border bins. For 12 regions, we have 11 border bins. Since we know that the total number of bins in our histogram is 1310, the border bins are $\{107, 214, 321, 428, 535, 642, 749, 856, 963, 1070, 1177\}$. We identify two potential true-ToFs as duplicates of each other when they fall within ± 16 bins of a border bin. The margin is set to 16 bins because it is the width of the flash LiDAR pulse of our datasets. From now on, the vicinity of 16bins on either side of a border is referred to as “border region”.

In figure 3.2, border number 7, that is at bin number 749, has two potential true-ToFs, at bins 740 and 755, one on either side within the margin of 16 bins. Let us call the bin on the left b_L and the bin on the right b_R . The p-values of b_L and b_R are $p(b_L)$ and $p(b_R)$, respectively. When such a phenomenon occurs, we manipulate the p-values of the duplicates as follows:

Algorithm 1: Manipulation of p-values of duplicates.

Data: $p(b_L)$ and $p(b_R)$
Result: Revised $p(b_L)$ and $p(b_R)$.

```

1 if  $p(b_L) + p(b_R) > 1$  then
2   |  $p_{\text{total}} = 1$ ;
3 else
4   |  $p_{\text{total}} = p(b_L) + p(b_R)$ ;
5 end
6 if  $p(b_L) \geq p(b_R)$  then
7   |  $p(b_L) = p_{\text{total}}$ ;
8   |  $p(b_R) = 0$ ;
9 else
10  |  $p(b_L) = 0$ ;
11  |  $p(b_R) = p_{\text{total}}$ ;
12 end

```

In algorithm 1 we revise the p-values of the duplicates. We maximize the p-value of that duplicate which already has higher certainty and nullify the p-value of the other. Though we do not know which of them represents the peak more accurately, we take a chance by relying on their p-values to retain one and eliminate the other. This technique does not have a scientific justi-

fication. However, it is a heuristic way of eliminating one of the duplicates. The elimination itself takes place in stages 2 (section 3.2.2) and 4 (section 3.3.2) as these stages eliminate points solely based on their p-values.

Figure 3.2: A section of bar graph that represents the p-values of two potential true-ToFs that are duplicates of each other. Here, the potential true-ToFs $\{740, 755\}$ are within the margin of 16 bins of border-7.

3.2.2 Stage 2: Conditional Otsu Filtering

In this stage, we adapt Otsu and Multi-Otsu algorithms and eliminate some elements of each V_{ToF} that have low p-values. Figure 3.3 represents p-value vs. potential true-ToF bar graphs of four histograms. Each of the bar graphs represents an object at 36m at $r_b = 2, 4, 6, 8\text{MHz}$, respectively. The bar graphs depict two types of bins: the ones with significant p-value and others with relatively insignificant p-values. Figure 3.3a represents one bin with a very high p-value and another with a very small yet noticeable p-value. The remaining ten p-values are invisibly small. Figure 3.3c represents eight bins with significant p-values and four bins with insignificant p-values. In this stage, we eliminate some of the potential true-ToFs of each V_{ToF} , which have insignificant p-values in their corresponding V_p .

The conditional Otsu filtering in this stage automatically generates one or two unique thresholds for each unique pair of V_{ToF} and V_p in an unsupervised manner. The number of thresholds depends on the modality of the histogram of the elements of V_p . Thus, the elements of V_{ToF} are divided into two or

three classes. The potential true-ToFs whose p-values are below the lowest threshold are eliminated.

Figure 3.3: Probability vs. potential true-ToF bar graphs of an object at 36m in x-direction at various r_b s.

As mentioned in 2.5.1, the Otsu algorithm works best for bi-modal distributions. However, the histograms of elements of V_p are not always bi-modal as shown in figure 3.4. The conditional Otsu filtering stage responds dynamically to the distribution of the elements of a V_p as shown in the figure 3.5. The word “multi-modal” in the figure 3.5 refers to modes greater than two.

The algorithm takes a pair of V_p and V_{ToF} as input. Suppose the distribution of p-values has more than two modes. In that case, the algorithm generates two thresholds using the multi-Otsu algorithm, and the lowest threshold $t_{1,\text{multi-Otsu}}$ is considered for classification. On the other hand, if the distribution has only two modes, the algorithm generates one threshold t_{Otsu} . Then, all the potential true-ToFs whose p-values are less than the considered threshold $t_{1,\text{multi-Otsu}}$ or t_{Otsu} are eliminated. The remaining potential true-ToFs in each V_{ToF} are mapped into 3D space following the process mentioned

in section 2.3. In further stages, the point cloud is processed in 3D space.

Figure 3.4: Histograms of elements of V_{ToF} of an object at 24m distance at various r_b s. Figure (a) has two modes, figures (b) and (c) have three modes, and figure (d) has four modes.

3.3 Noise Reduction in 3D Space

3.3.1 Stage 3: Gaussian Filter for Probability Diffusion (GFPD)

The p-values of the points are not 100% accurate (section 5 in [2]). The accuracy of a p-value is characterized by its closeness to the ground truth. Ideally, the bin in V_{ToF} that is the true-ToF should have the highest p-value. After the point cloud goes through the above two stages of processing and is mapped into 3D space, many false points still appear in the point cloud (section 5.2). At this stage, the objects in the point cloud are still not

Figure 3.5: Flow chart of conditional filtering based on Otsu and Multi-Otsu algorithms.

clearly perceivable, as shown in figure 3.6. The x-axis in figure 3.6 is the one orthogonal to the image plane. This point cloud has many more points compared to its ground truth. From now on in this chapter, we visualize the effect of processing methods on this demo point cloud at different r_b values that belong to dataset 2 (section 4.2) to make the methods and their utility easy to understand.

The true points in the point cloud are only the ones that belong to the road surface, the car, and the wall, all of which are visible in figure 1.1. However, they submerge in a large number of false points in the resulting point cloud from stage 2 (section 3.2.2) as can be observed in figure 3.6.

Figure 3.6: The figure is a result of the conditional Otsu filtering whose ground truth point cloud is in figure 1.1, at $r_b = 4\text{MHz}$. The color of each point represents its p-value, where black is 0 (minimum), and red is 1 (maximum).

Also, there is a significant number of points whose p-values are noisy. Some false points have high p-values, and some true points have low p-values, which should not be the case ideally. The magnitude of noise in a p-value depends on two factors: distance from sensor and r_b (section 5 in [2]).

The false points are randomly distributed in the 3D space. On the other hand, the true points exist in clusters because they represent natural objects in the environment. Hence, most of the points have points of similar class (true/false) in their neighborhood, and some, in the surface region of the objects, have both true and false points. We leverage this fact and apply a smoothing filter on the p-values of the points to reduce the noise.

A bilateral filter smooths the outliers while preserving the edges by revising the pixel intensities with the weighted averages of neighboring pixel intensities. The bilateral weights depend on spatial closeness and intensity difference and it works best when the intensity of the outlier is not significantly different from its neighbors. In the opposite case, the filter assumes it is a border region and assigns a smaller weight to the outlier. In a 3D point cloud, the “border region” is the immediate space around the 3D objects.

In our point cloud, a significant number of outliers are within the neighborhood of the same class with a significantly different p-value. Hence, we removed the second term in the exponential function $w(P_{ij})$ (equation 2.11) to consider only the spatial closeness to calculate the weights. The resulting $w(P_{ij})$ is the frequency response function of a Gaussian filter (equation 3.1,

equation 3.2) and the weights calculated using it are Gaussian weights. The border regions limit the performance of this method.

$$p(P_i) = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^k p(P_{ij})w(P_{ij})}{\sum_{j=1}^k w(P_{ij})} \quad (3.1)$$

$$w(P_{ij}) = e^{-\frac{\|P_{ij}-P_i\|_2^2}{2\sigma_p^2}} \quad (3.2)$$

$p(P_i)$ represents the p-value of a point P_i in the point cloud and σ_p is the standard deviation of the Gaussian kernel. The effect of this filter on the point cloud in figure 3.6, whose top view is figure 3.7a, can be seen in figure 3.7b. The true points on the wall, which had low p-values previously, gained magnitude after applying this filter.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.7: (a) represents the top view of the point cloud in figure 3.6. (b) is the result of GFPD on (a).

This method smooths the p-values of the points within their neighborhood. In the next stage, we predict the class of each point, where the classes are: true and false. The prediction is solely based on p-values.

3.3.2 Stage 4: Probability Based Classification using Multi-linear Classifier (MLC)

From figure 3.3 we understand that the magnitude of p-values of true points is inversely proportional to r_b . Another fact is that the true points close to the sensor have a high p-value. Both of these phenomena occur for the same reason: the simulator is efficient in recognizing the true points when the peak in the TCSPC histogram is pronounced. The ease of detecting the peak is higher under low r_b (section I.A of [9]), that is the background photon rate, and close distance (section IV.C of [9]). The reason for the former is that the noise in the peak is proportional to r_b , and the latter is that the intensity of the reflected signal has an inverse quadratic proportionality with distance. We leverage these facts in this section.

Though the laser pulse travels radially, we consider the distance in x-dimension in this stage. We do so because we aim for a small field of view and a long range, which is usually the case in flash LiDAR. In such conditions, the difference between the radial- and x-distance vanishes. In the following paragraphs, A and B, we explain how we deal with the point clouds with r_b up to 2MHz, and greater than 2MHz, respectively.

A. $r_b \leq 2\text{MHz}$: The demo point cloud at $r_b = 2\text{MHz}$ goes through the above processing stages 1, 2, and 3. The figure 3.8 is the p-values vs. x-distances scatter plot of the points of the resulting point cloud. We can observe that the p-value is greater than 0.8 for almost all the points in the point cloud. Also, this point cloud is a good example to acquire a general perspective of the range of p-values with distance, as it contains true points across the complete range. Hence, if the $r_b \leq 2\text{MHz}$, we apply a constant threshold $g_c = 0.8$ and filter the points with p-values above it to the next stage.

We can notice, in the scatter plot, that this strategy would eliminate a noticeable number of true points at x-distance > 45 m. Though these points are labeled true points, they are far from their true position. This phenomenon occurs because the preceding research work [2] considers a tolerance of $\pm 5\%$, in the bin position of ToF, to label a point as a true point. 5% translates to a significant value in absolute length when the point is far from the sensor. Hence, eliminating these so-called true points, which from

Figure 3.8: A scatter plot of p-value vs. x-distance of all the points in the point cloud after the demo point cloud (figure 1.1), at $r_b = 2\text{MHz}$, passes stage 3.

now on are referred to as sparse true points, is not a significant loss.

The p-values start dropping their magnitude after 30m. Though the drop is small enough to apply a global threshold still, it becomes significant when $r_b > 2\text{MHz}$. Hence, we must generate a threshold for the p-value of a point by adapting to its distance.

B. $r_b > 2\text{MHz}$: As the magnitude of p-values drops with x-distance at $r_b > 2\text{MHz}$, we notice three different regions in the scatter plot. These regions are particularly distinct at high r_b , i.e., $r_b \geq 5\text{MHz}$, in terms of their p-values. We define these regions by the range of x. In regions 1, 2 and 3, the range of $x \in [0, 30)$, $[30, 40)$ and $[40, 60]$, respectively.

The p-values are almost always greater than 0.8 in region 1. Hence, we apply a constant threshold, g_c , on this region irrespective of r_b . Applying a global threshold also avoids computational overload. We intend the method developed in this thesis for a system-on-chip (SOC) application. An SOC has limited processing power and memory. Though we would like to obtain the best possible results, the possibility is limited by the capabilities of an SOC. Hence, computationally cheap algorithms are the preferred option. Nevertheless, we do not compromise on quality but leverage the opportunities to reduce computational effort, which leads us toward a pragmatic solution.

Figure 3.9: A scatter plot of p-value vs. x-distance of all the points in the point cloud when the demo point cloud (figure 1.1), at $r_b = 6\text{MHz}$, passes stage 3.

The p-values start falling in region 2. Nevertheless, true points are still predominantly distinguishable from false points, as shown in figure 3.9. They start to merge in region 3, which makes this region the most challenging one for classification. For these reasons, we develop separate classifiers for regions 2 and 3. To this end, we have multiple options, such as linear classifiers, support vector machines (SVM), decision trees, and deep neural networks. From the distribution observed in the scatter plot, it became apparent that a simple linear classifier would be able to classify the points in region 2 correctly. It would retain more false points in region 3 than in region 2, relatively more at higher r_b . Nevertheless, false points are primarily sparse, and there is still a sparsity-based outlier removal stage after this stage. Therefore, we can afford to retain some false points, at this stage, with the advantage of removing many of them using one of the simplest classifiers, such as the multi-linear one we use.

We use the exhaustive line fitting method with F1-score as an optimization metric to develop the classifiers. Here, for the classification line, the x-axis is the x-distance, and the y-axis is the p-value. The blue dotted lines, in figure 3.10 represent the borders of the aforementioned regions. Consider, for instance, region 2, i.e., $x = [30, 40)$. The left and right borders are divided with a step size of 0.01. All possible combinations of a point on the left

border and a point on the right border are tested, by generating line equations, for classification, seeking the best F1 score. We apply a pre-condition that the slope of the classifier should be negative, as the average p-value of true and false points decreases as the x-distance increases, as shown in figure 3.10. Hence, the classifier should also have a negative slope to adapt to this relationship between the p-value and x-distance.

Thus, we obtain linear classifiers for regions 2 and 3 for the demo point cloud at $3\text{MHz} \leq r_b \leq 8\text{MHz}$. The red lines in figure 3.10 represent the linear classifiers. The points above the classification line are filtered to the next stage.

This thesis has two datasets: datasets 1 and 2, which are explained in section 4.2. The point clouds on which the MLCs are trained are the samples of dataset 2. We chose dataset 2 for training because its true points are spatially more homogeneous than dataset 1, making it more suitable for generalization. The parameters of Stages 3 and 5 are also fine-tuned on dataset 2 for the same reason. To test for the generalization, we apply the method on datasets 1 and 2, in section 5.2, and compare the results.

Hereon, the p-values of the true and false points are similar and thus cannot be used for further filtering. On the other hand, the remaining false points are significantly more sparse than the true points. This can be noticed in region 3 of the scatter plot shown in figure 3.10. We leverage this fact to further remove false points in the next and final stage of the proposed method.

3.3.3 Stage 5: Dynamic Statistical Outlier Removal (DSOR)

A regular SOR filter (section 2.4) works best under either or both of the following conditions:

- The density of true points is uniform over the domain.
- The density of true and false points is significantly different over the domain.

Since the laser pulses travel radially, the point cloud density decreases with radial distance. Hence, the former condition does not hold in our case. At close distances, say region 1 and sometimes region 2, the density of true and false points is significantly different in our point clouds. However, their densities are similar at large distances, say region 3. Therefore, the second condition also does not hold in our case. This demands an outlier removal algorithm that adapts to distance and r_b . Hence, we implement the dynamic statistical outlier removal (DSOR) algorithm.

Figure 3.10: The figure represents the same scatter plot as in figure 3.9 with additional information of the multi-linear classifier and borders of the regions 1, 2, and 3.

DSOR is developed in [20] to remove the undesired points that result from falling snow. These undesired points are near the sensor, and their density varies (reduces) with distance. The density of these undesired points is greater than the true (desired) points. In other words, this algorithm is intended to remove the points in dense clusters. In our case, the opposite applies because the density of undesired points is lower than the desired points. Nevertheless, the parameters of the DSOR algorithm can be fine-tuned to remove the sparse points rather than the denser ones. Refer to section 4.4.2 for the fine-tuning processes and fine-tuned parameters.

DSOR is an extension of SOR (section 2.4). In SOR, we calculate the mean absolute distance (MAD) of each point to its n -nearest neighbors (equation 2.6). Then, we compute a global threshold g_{MAD} and apply it to the MAD of each point. The points with a MAD greater than g_{MAD} are filtered. The threshold is constant for all the points in the point cloud, irrespective of their distance. The performance of this method is limited if the ranges of MADs of true and false points overlap. This overlapping phenomenon does occur in our case, which makes SOR less desirable to remove the outliers in our point clouds. This is where the DSOR comes into the picture. In DSOR, a unique threshold (d_{MAD}) is calculated for each point. The threshold is a function of g_{MAD} , distance and a tunable parameter (f_{DSOR}), as shown in

equation 3.3.

$$d_{\text{MAD}}(P_i) = g_{\text{MAD}} p_i^x f_{\text{DSOR}} \quad (3.3)$$

In the equation 3.3, P_i is a point in the point cloud, and p_i^x is its x-coordinate. Thus, we implement a sparsity-based outlier removal method, DSOR, which adapts to the distance of the point. We further extended this algorithm by making the tunable parameter f_{SOR} a function of r_b which is explained in section 4.4.2. This is because, at low r_b or in short distances, many false points are already eliminated in the earlier stages, but at high r_b or large distances, more false points pass through the previous stages. Hence, making the algorithm adaptive to r_b and p_i^x ensures that we use all the information at hand.

Chapter 4

Experiments

This chapter contains four sections. In section 4.1, we explain the hardware and the software environments in which the data processing is performed in this thesis. The work we performed is based on two datasets: dataset 1 and dataset 2. These datasets are introduced in section 4.2. Further, section 4.3 contains analysis on the quality of V_{ToFS} of the point clouds of the two datasets. In the end, section 4.4 explains how the parameters of stage 3 (section 3.3.1) and stage 5 (section 3.3.3) are tuned.

4.1 Development Environment

Hardware Specifications: A Lenovo™IdeaPad™C340 with 8GB RAM, and 500GB SSD secondary memory, running on an Intel™®Core™i5-8265U CPU, is used for the development. The computer runs on a 64bit Windows™operating system.

Software Specifications: The algorithms are implemented in Python. The simplicity of Python’s syntax is helpful for rapid experimentation. It provides the following open-source libraries, which we make use of in this work:

Matplotlib: This library provides plotting and visualizing tools for numerical and statistical data [25] in Python and MATLAB. The plots include pie charts, bar charts, histograms, scatter plots, line graphs, contour plots, polar plots, etc. We use this library to generate the histograms of intensities of an image (figure 2.4b), a bar chart of p-values of various bin numbers (figure 2.6), and scatter plots of x-distances vs. p-values of the points in a point cloud (figure 3.8).

Pandas is a data analysis library that provides data structures to store

data [26]. Its conditional methods efficiently search for particular information in a large data container. It also provides tools to load data from storage. We used this library only to load the data into the program. We used NumPy for data storage and manipulation purposes.

OS: This library supports interaction with the operating system. It sets the program’s directory, files, and datasets.

NumPy: This library provides support in generating and storing multi-dimensional numerical arrays, and matrices [27]. It is used in this project for the same purposes. In addition, it provides many mathematical operations to manipulate data. Like Pandas, it provides conditional methods to search for information in large data containers. However, unlike Pandas, it is compatible with other libraries like Matplotlib, scikit-image, and Open3D.

Open3D: It is a 3D data processing library that is available in both Python and C++ [28]. It provides data structures, data processing, manipulation algorithms, and visualization functions for 3D data, especially for point clouds of multiple formats like (x,y,z) , (x,y,z,r,g,b) , (x,y,z,i) , etc. We use this library to visualize the 3D point cloud, assign a color to each point, and find n-nearest neighbors.

Scikit-Image: This is an image processing library that provides algorithms for image filtering, segmentation, feature detection, image balancing, etc., [29]. We used this library to implement the Otsu and multi-Otsu algorithms.

4.2 Datasets

We use two datasets in this project: datasets 1 and 2. The ground truth scenes for both datasets were captured in the CARLA simulator environment at Fraunhofer IMS [30]. We have processed them using the point cloud simulator 2.2.

The simulator accounts for the inverse quadratic relationship between the distance and the intensity of the laser pulse by considering a maximum intensity of 28×10^9 Hz at the closest point, i.e., at a 5m distance. However, it does not simulate the surface characteristics of the obstacle material.

4.2.1 Dataset 1

This dataset is a set of 8 point clouds. Each point cloud represents the ground truth scene in figure 4.1 at a unique r_b ranging from 1MHz to 8MHz.

A car at 25m in this scene falls at one of the 12 border regions of the histogram. The border region (section 3.2.1) refers to the vicinity of 16bins

Figure 4.1: The ground truth point cloud of dataset 1, where there is a car at 25m distance, road surface, and a wall at 50m.

on either side of any of the 11 borders that divide the histogram (section 2.2). Hence, we choose this dataset to test the performance of the border-effect suppression stage (section 3.2.1).

4.2.2 Dataset 2

This dataset is a set of 8 point clouds. Each point cloud represents the ground truth scene in figure 1.1 at a unique r_b ranging from 1MHz to 8MHz.

The points in this scene cover almost the entire field of view in the x, y, and z domains.

4.3 Validity of the Vectors of Potential True-ToFs

A V_{ToF} is a vector that contains 12 potential true-ToFs of a histogram. It is valid when at least one of its 12 elements represents the ground truth. Some of the V_{ToF} s do not contain a true-ToF because of the performance limitation of the point cloud simulator, as explained in section 2.2. Hence, we analyzed datasets 1 and 2 to identify their composition in terms of valid and invalid V_{ToF} s.

We are performing this analysis to identify the quality of the V_{ToF} s. This is important because they are the input to the proposed method.

Figure 4.2: The figure represents the percentage of valid V_{ToF} s of the samples in datasets 1 and 2.

Figure 4.2 displays the percentage of valid V_{ToF} s with respect to r_b . We can draw two inferences from the graph:

- The percentage of valid V_{ToF} s is inversely proportional to r_b .

Reason: The ToF peak becomes less obvious as the r_b increases, which makes it difficult for the point cloud simulator to identify the peak.

- Dataset 1 has more valid V_{ToF} s than dataset 2.

Reason: The main difference between the two datasets is that the car in dataset 1 is closer than it is in dataset 2. The clarity of the ToF peak is directly proportional to the object's distance. Hence, the simulator can generate more valid V_{ToF} s from dataset 1 than from dataset 2.

4.4 Parameter Tuning

In this section, we tune the parameters of stages 3 and 5 in subsections 4.4.1 and 4.4.2 respectively. This tuning process is based on dataset 2 because the points of it are more homogeneous in the x-domain, as explained in section 3.3.2. The homogeneity in the x-domain is vital because we want to make stages 3, 4, and 5 adaptive to x-distance. The distribution of points in dataset

1, in the x-domain, is skewed. We are using only one dataset for tuning the parameters, despite having less data because combining both datasets would lead to a skewed distribution of points in the x-domain.

4.4.1 GFPD Parameter

The standard deviation σ_p is a tunable parameter in GFPD (equation 3.2). We systematically applied various values for σ_p and observed the mean squared error (MSE). Here, the MSE is between the p-values of each point after applying GFPD and their labels. Each point has a label of 0 or 1. 0 for false points and 1 for true points. These should also be the ideal p-values of the points. Hence, this is a relevant metric to identify the best σ_p value.

To perform this analysis, we chose a point cloud in dataset 2 at $r_b = 6\text{MHz}$. This is because it is more important that the method works at higher r_b since the data at lower r_b is relatively straightforward to process. Considering $4\text{MHz} \leq r_b \leq 8\text{MHz}$ to be the higher range, 6MHz is the median.

Figure 4.3: The graph represents the characteristic of the standard deviation parameter σ_p concerning the Mean Squared Error.

In figure 4.3 we notice that the MSE saturates nearly at $\sigma_p = 1.5$. Hence, we assign $\sigma_p = 1.5$.

4.4.2 DSOR Parameters

The DSOR has two tunable parameters: f_{SOR} and f_{DSOR} . The factor to which we are applying the threshold here is the MAD (mean absolute distance) of each point, to its n -nearest neighbors, in the point cloud. The μ_{MAD} of true points should be less than that of false points. We eliminate the points whose MAD is above a certain threshold. However, the false points at low x -distance have similar MAD to the true points at large x -distance. The f_{SOR} parameter modifies the preliminary global threshold of a point cloud (equation 2.6), while the f_{DSOR} helps us vary the threshold with x -distance (equation 3.3).

At low r_b , the p -values of almost all the true points are significantly greater than those of the false points. Hence, most points in the point cloud are true by the time it reaches the last stage of processing (figure 4.4a). Hence, in the DSOR stage, we need to preserve most of the points except those with extremely high MAD. We tuned f_{SOR} by incrementing its value from 0.1 to 3.0, with a step size of 0.1. It is noticed that at $f_{\text{SOR}} = 2.5$, false points in the point cloud are eliminated without mistakenly removing many true points (figure 4.4).

At medium r_b , say $3\text{MHz} \leq r_b < 6\text{MHz}$, considerable number of false points are still present in the point cloud. Hence, we need to remove more false points than before. This gives us a slightly lower f_{SOR} value. Following the same tuning approach as for low r_b , we found that $f_{\text{SOR}} = 0.5$ yields best results. Lastly, for the point clouds at high r_b , say $6\text{MHz} \leq r_b \leq 8\text{MHz}$, $f_{\text{SOR}} = 0.1$ suits the best.

We followed a similar analytical approach and arrived at an optimal f_{DSOR} for all the values of r_b . See figure 4.5 for the results on a demo point cloud at various f_{DSOR} values. $f_{\text{DSOR}} = 0.02$ gives effective results.

Figure 4.4: (a) is the result for the demo point cloud at $r_b = 2\text{MHz}$ after stage 4. (a) transforms to (b), (c), and (d) when subjected to stage 5 with $f_{\text{SOR}} = 0.5, 1.5,$ and $2.5,$ respectively, and $f_{\text{DSOR}} = 0.02.$

Figure 4.5: (a) is the result for the demo point cloud at $r_b = 2\text{MHz}$ after stage 4. (a) transforms to (b), (c), and (d) when subjected to stage 5 with $f_{\text{DSOR}} = 0.002, 0.02,$ and $0.2,$ respectively, and $f_{\text{SOR}} = 0.5.$

Chapter 5

Results

In this chapter, the proposed method is evaluated to analyze its performance. In section 5.1, the performance of the border effect suppression phenomenon is tested on dataset 1. Further, section 5.2 demonstrates the number of true and false points in the point cloud after each stage. This section helps understand the stage-wise performance of the proposed method. Finally, in section 5.3, we compare the performance of the proposed method with the standard method.

5.1 Results of Border-Effect Suppression

The proposed method applies the border-effect suppression stage (stage 1) on every input point cloud. However, this stage changes the input only when duplicates exist in the point cloud. Duplicates occur when an object falls in 11 border regions, as explained in section 2.2. In dataset 1, a car is present at 25m that falls near a border bin. When the point cloud simulator generates V_{ToFS} of those histograms whose potential true-ToFs fall on the borders, it generates duplicates. Hence, we test this method on point clouds whose r_b s are 3MHz and 7MHz, respectively, of dataset 1. We chose these samples to show the results at lower and higher ranges of r_b .

We notice that the border-effect suppression stage is showing positive results as shown in Figure 5.1. In a pair of duplicates, this stage nullifies the p-value of the duplicate that has the lowest p-value. Figures 5.1a and 5.1c are snippets of the 3MHz and 7MHz point clouds, respectively, when they are subjected to stage 2, conditional Otsu, directly, without undergoing stage 1, border effect suppression. In these figures, the dark points in the cluster representing the car are duplicate points. On the other hand, when the same point clouds undergo both border effect suppression and conditional Otsu

filtering, we notice the removal of duplicates, as shown in figures 5.1b and 5.1d. We showed snippets of the point clouds because it is difficult to notice the duplicates in the complete ones.

Figure 5.1: (a) and (c) are 3MHz and 7MHz point clouds, respectively, of dataset 1, after stage 2 without border-effect suppression. (b) and (d) are the same after stage 2 with border-effect suppression.

5.2 Stage-Wise Results

Since the proposed method has multiple stages, it is wise to analyze the performance of individual stages. As we already know, stages 1 and 3 are data manipulation, while stages 2, 4, and 5 are filtering stages. Hence, we do not notice the removal of points in stages 1 and 3. This section evaluates the stage-wise results on dataset 1 and dataset 2. Figure 5.2 demonstrates the number of false points in the point clouds after each stage of processing, and

figure 5.3 demonstrates the number of true points in the point cloud after each stage. Stage 0 is the stage before the data processing begins.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5.2: (a) and (b) represent the number of false points in the point cloud after each stage of dataset 1 and dataset 2, respectively. Each line in the graphs represents a unique sample of the respective datasets.

We notice, in figure 5.2, for both the datasets, that the majority of the false points are eliminated at stage 2, followed by stages 4 and 5. It is easier to distinguish the true and false points in the initial stages than in the latter. We notice that the difficulty in removing the false points increases with r_b .

(a)

(b)

Figure 5.3: (a) and (b) represent the number of true points in the point cloud after each stage of dataset 1 and dataset 2, respectively. Each line in the graphs represents a unique sample of the respective datasets.

On the other hand, in figure 5.3, we notice that we lose a large number of true points in stage 2, followed by stage 5. As the r_b increases, we lose many true points in each filtering stage. This is an evidence that the accuracy of p-values decreases with the increase in r_b . Though we can allow more true points to pass through stage 2 by scaling down the threshold, because of their very low p-values, they will get eliminated in stage 4.

Figure 5.4: (a) The result of a 5MHz sample of dataset 2 after stage 1 processing and (b) after stage two processing.

In addition, we can notice an agreement in the results of dataset 1 and dataset 2, with respect to the number of false points removed and true points retained in different stages. Consider, for example, at $r_b = 5\text{MHz}$, the MLC (stage 3) removes 99.05% and 98.48% false points of datasets 1 and 2, respectively, from the input to that stage. Further, the same stage retains 95.70% and 95.55% true points of the same samples, respectively, from its input. The results of the further stages are also in agreement, as shown in the figures 5.2 and 5.3. We have trained the multi-linear classifiers and tuned the parameters of the Gaussian filter and DSOR on dataset 2. This agreement proves that the proposed method generalized well to dataset 1.

We also demonstrate a point cloud's evolution through the processing stages. Figure 5.4 represents the point cloud after stages 1 and 2 in sub-figures 5.4a and 5.4b, respectively, where the point cloud is processed in the histogram space. Though in the method, we do not map the points

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5.5: (a) The result of a 5MHz sample of dataset 2 after stage 3 processing, (b) after stage 4 processing, and (c) after stage 5 processing.

into 3D space after stage 1, we have done so to generate the graphics for demonstration. Then, figure 5.5 represents the point cloud after stages 3, 4 and 5 in sub-figures 5.5a, 5.5b, and 5.5c, respectively, where the point cloud is processed in 3D space. In these figures, we can observe the evolution of the point cloud as it sheds many false and some true points and arrives at the stage where the objects in the point cloud are identifiable. The difference in the number of false points between figures 5.4a and 5.5c is the result of the proposed multistage noise reduction method.

5.3 Multistage Noise Reduction Method vs. Standard Method

In this section, we demonstrate the final results of the multistage noise reduction method on dataset 2 and compare them with the standard method results.

Figure 5.6 shows the point clouds of dataset 2 whose $r_b = 2, 4, 6,$ and 8MHz that have undergone the multistage noise reduction processing. Here we see that the point clouds are almost clear from the noise and very close to the ground truth. Except at 8MHz , the false points remain in the point cloud at a larger distance at the wall. On the other hand, Figure 5.7 demonstrates the point clouds of dataset 2 whose $r_b = 2, 4, 6,$ and 8MHz that have undergone the standard method processing. Here we can notice that the final result of the 2MHz point cloud appears to have no noise. However, from 4MHz , more and more false points start to remain in the point cloud. With increasing r_b , the wall in the point clouds fades away. This is because, in the first stage of the standard method, we select the bin in the histogram with the highest p-value. Therefore, in all the cases when the true-ToF is not the bin that has the highest p-value, we miss it. In addition, in the second stage, the SOR algorithm is not adaptive to the changing density of the point cloud with the distance from the sensor. Hence, it eliminates true and false points whose neighboring density is beyond a fixed threshold.

We demonstrate the percentage of false points removed and the true points retained, for both methods, concerning the input proportions, in each sample of dataset 2 in figures 5.8a and 5.8b, respectively. We notice that for $r_b \leq 2\text{MHz}$, both the standard and multistage noise reduction methods remove a similar percentage of false points from the point cloud. From 2MHz to 4MHz , the multistage method slightly outperforms the standard method. Beyond 4MHz , the multistage method outperforms the standard method by a large margin. This margin at 6 and 8MHz is 0.98% and 1.81% , respectively.

On the other hand, the standard method retains 2% more true points than the multistage method at $r_b = 1\text{MHz}$. However, from 2MHz, the multistage method outperforms the standard method in this regard too. Beyond 6MHz, the standard method retains less than 50% of the true points. The multistage method retains 66% of the true points even at the worst case, i.e., at 8MHz. Thus, the proposed method performs better than the standard method in terms of the percentage of removed false points and preserved true points.

Figure 5.6: Visualisations of point clouds of dataset 2 after multistage noise reduction method processing.

Figure 5.7: Visualisations of point clouds of dataset 2 after standard method processing.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5.8: (a) represents the percentage of false points removed from each sample of dataset 2 and (b) represents the percentage of true points retained of the same, using the standard and the multistage noise reduction methods.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

We have successfully developed and implemented a novel multistage noise reduction method for point cloud processing with p-value information. We have developed a stage-wise method, where each stage solves a particular problem. Stage 1 deals with the duplicates in the point clouds. Stage 2 removes obvious false points automatically. Stage 3 attempts to homogenize the p-values in the point cloud. Stage 4 again attempts to remove false points based on the p-values. Finally, stage 5 removes sparse false points.

In this development, we used our understanding of the physical characteristics of light and the p-values at hand. This way, we fully use the available information to solve the problem. This helped us develop a method that is not solely data-dependent but also complies with physics and the nature of the point cloud simulator.

We made the method dynamic to the point cloud's background photon rate, distance, and density. This makes it an intelligent algorithm that can adapt to multiple scenes. It also gives the readers multiple options to tune the algorithm for their use case. We made use of the MSE and F1-score metrics to compute optimal parameters. We not only tuned the parameters of stages 4 and 5 based on the data but also explained the scientific nature of these parameters and their characteristics concerning distance and background photon rate. This explanation would be helpful for the readers to adapt the algorithm for different use cases.

As we stated in the introduction, the additional p-value information for each point in the point cloud is unprecedented in point cloud processing literature, and we wanted to test its utility and limitation. We designed an experimental evaluation to that end. We designed the stages in our method to take advantage of all the information we have in the point cloud to identify and remove false points. As stated in the introduction, we also used spatial correlations by implementing nearest neighbors-based processing in stages 3

and 5.

Since our method has five stages, it could be challenging to know the contribution of each stage to the final result. To this end, we also demonstrated each stage's performance by its impact on the result. We showed the false points removed and the true points retained in each stage. Further, since the proposed method is developed on dataset 2, we tested its performance on dataset 1, in addition to dataset 2. We found that the results on the two datasets agree with each other.

We engineered a standard method based on popular and standard practices of point cloud processing. To understand the progress in the research, we compared the results of the proposed and standard methods.

The proposed method outperforms the standard method by a large margin. This suggests that the p-values helped distinguish the true and false points and that we successfully used them. Also, we have identified that the utility of the p-value saturates, at stage 4 of the proposed method, while a non-negligible number of false points still remain in the point cloud. The standard method performs well only at low background photon rates, but the proposed method performs well at low, medium, and partially at high background photon rates. There is scope for improvement at large distances at high background photon rates.

Chapter 7

Scope for Future Research

In stage 4, we implemented a multi-linear classifier to classify the points into true and false candidates. Here, we have noticed that the classifier is not efficient in the third region at high background photon rates. Therefore, other options, such as SVM, decision trees, or deep neural networks, can be tested for the classifier. In addition, we have considered x-distance in stages 4 and 5. Instead, the radial distance can be tested to verify if it results in better performance of the method.

The method should be implemented on a hardware component, like an FPGA, to test its latency and memory requirements. This helps in understanding if there is scope to increase the algorithm's complexity, involving deep neural networks, etc.

The proposed method should be tested on a larger dataset like KITTI. The datasets considered in this thesis are simple, as they only have two objects. The method should be tested in complex scenes with a higher number of and more types of objects, such as pedestrians, street lamps, bikes, babies, etc. Also, in stage 4, we divide the point cloud into three regions. This should also be tested in point clouds of a more extensive range and flash LiDARs of higher and lower power. It should be tested whether the point cloud needs to be divided into more regions for a more extensive range.

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